

Framework to Embed Machine Learning Algorithms in P-graph: Communication from the Chemical Process Perspectives

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Abstract:

P-graph is a popularly used framework for process network synthesis (PNS) and network topological optimization. This *short communication* introduces a Python interface for P-graph to serve as a linkage to modern programming ecosystems. This allows for a wider application of the fast and efficient P-graph solver, to provide structural and topological enumeration in numerous fields. The proposed framework allows for more integrative usage in Artificial Intelligence (AI), machine learning, process system engineering, chemical engineering and chemometrics. Large and repetitive topologies can also be automated using the new programming interface, saving time and effort in modelling. This *short communication* serves as a demonstration of the newly developed open-sourced P-graph interface.

Keywords: P-graph, Process Network Synthesis, Programming Interface, Python

1. The Classical P-Graph Framework

The P-graph framework is originally introduced in the early 1990s (Friedler et al., 1993, 1992) to solve large PNS problems with low computation effort. P-graphs are bi-partite graphs with different nodes for materials and operating units, while having arcs with arrows to describe the direction of material. Axioms in the P-graph framework ensure that materials and operating units are well-defined, materials flows are directed, and source-demand nodes are properly differentiated (Friedler et al., 1993, 1992).

The efficient algorithms, freely available software, and attractive graphical interface have since then contributed to many developments in various research fields. including azeotropic distillation systems (Feng et al., 2003), downstream chemical process design (Liu et al., 2004), regional renewable energy networks (Lam et al., 2010), chemical reaction networks (Fan et al., 2012), biomass supply chains (How et al., 2016), hydrogen networks (Tan et al., 2021), product formulation (Lim et al., 2021), and aquaponics resource optimization (Ondruška et al., 2022). P-graph has also been described in a widely-taught undergraduate textbook (Peters et al., 2016) and recently comprehensively described in a specialized textbook (Friedler et al., 2022).

The hybrid uses of P-graph and various machine learning, data analysis, chemometrics models, etc., are gaining popularity fast. For example, the machine learning platform WEKA was used with P-graph to provide waste conversion technology selection (Ali et al., 2022). Artificial neural networks were also

embedded into the P-graph software for unit modelling purposes (How et al., 2019). Although some simple models were possible, the scalability of such application is limited due to the necessity of manual and static specification of the problem network in P-Graph Studio. Furthermore, the incorporation of modern programming ecosystem was not possible, making research development for hybrid methods extremely challenging.

2. Method and New Library Introduction

This *short communication* introduces an open-sourced *Pgraph python library* (i) to automate problem specification and (ii) to act as an interface from the P-graph framework to modern Python programming ecosystems (Fig.1 (a)). The basic workflow of the library (Fig. 1(b)) can be summarized as the following:

Step 1: Start by specifying the problem network (G) using *NetworkX* (Hagberg et al., 2008) in a directed graph structure.

Step 2: The solver information, which contains G , the solver type, maximum number of solutions and mutual exclusion list, is then provided as argument in the P-graph initialization function. The P-graph initialized object (P) accepts all the generic P-graph solvers.

Step 2.1: After setting up the problem, users are recommended to visualize the problem network to visually check the inputs and initialization.

Step 3: The *run* function is used to call the backend P-graph solver and read the solution within P .

Step 3.1: The original network problem and its corresponding solutions, can be visualized via the *plot_solution* function.

Step 3.2: Exported to the original P-Graph Studio for manual editing with the *to_studio* function.

For additional functionalities, bi-directional communication is possible via the P-graph Python library, and solutions from solving the network problem can also be converted back to *NetworkX* objects in Python.

Figure 1: (a) Proposed Pgraph Python library and its integration into current frameworks. (b) Basic workflow and functionalities of Pgraph Python library.

To demonstrate the usability of the newly developed library. Three easily reproducible and illustrative examples are provided in Sections 3.1, 3.2, and 3.3 with the corresponding code in the supplementary materials. The corresponding examples and their demonstrated functionality are tabulated in Table 1 below.

Table 1: Case study demonstrations and their purposes

No.	Case Study	Demonstration	Contribution
3.1	Generic reaction pathway selection problem considering costs	Automatic capabilities to perform topology optimization with mutual exclusion	Automatic P-graph construction with full functionalities. Allows for automation of network structures previously not possible.

3.2	Embedding a machine learning algorithm trained on the diabetes dataset (Efron et al., 2004) into P-graph	Novel possibilities to automatically embed machine learning algorithms in P-graph	Automatic embedding of machine learning models via graph structures in P-graph is previously not possible.
3.3	Gas reservoir selection considering hydrate prediction in pipelines	Synergistic use of process optimization and machine learning models in P-graph	Embedding machine learning models with possibilities to add elements via P-graph studio. Allow the novel synergy of predictive models and process network optimization.

3.1 Automating Topology Problems with Mutual Exclusion

A chemical reaction pathway selection problem is shown in Fig. 2(a) with two separate reaction pathways having different conversions and associated costs. The purpose is to find the most cost-effective pathway to produce product D (i.e., material D). this problem allows only one reactor, imposing a mutual exclusion condition (red in Fig. 2(b)). From Fig. 2 (b), the problem can be effectively represented as a directed graph object and visualized graphically. *Pgraph Python library* identifies both pathways as viable solutions, proposing solution #1, i.e., reactor 2, as more economical than #2 (Fig. 2(c)), with total cost being 28,936.5 \$/year lower. This example demonstrates that *Pgraph Python library* allows for automatic network structure specification and solution analysis with the full functionalities of P-graph framework (to solve topological network optimization problems with mutual exclusion possibilities).

Figure 2: (a) Parameters for chemical reaction pathway selection problem. (b) Topology of the generated original problem. (c) Solution #1 selecting reactor 2 as an economic solution. (d) Solution #2 selecting reactor 1 as a viable solution.

3.2 Embedding Machine Learning Algorithms

Pgraph Python library also automatically embeds machine learning algorithms. Analyses of the diabetes dataset (Efron et al., 2004) and partial least squares (PLS) supervised learning model (Wold, 1980) (Fig 3(a)) identified factors that cause the maximum response for diabetes. In this dataset, various predictors from patient (age, sex, body-mass index, blood pressure, and blood serums at 4 different places of the body) is used to predict their diabetes level. To train the model, the data was normalized and 5-fold cross validation is performed. Since PLS is a cross-decomposition linear model, the model coefficients (\tilde{B}) can be automatically embedded via *Pgraph Python library* by representing the prediction as directed graph (see Fig. 3(b)). The key factors can be identified by maximizing the response value, which results in the solution in Fig. 3(c). The cost in the P-graph model makes sure that

the response is maximized, showing solutions with high diabetes level to low. The importance of each factor is represented by the value on the edges, highlighting the advantage of showing feature importance visually. This demonstrates the visual advantage of automatic P-graph and data-driven applications. Other machine learning models, such as support vector machines, neural networks, etc. can also be embedded via this method. For this specific problem, the combination of the most important variables can be analysed by cycling through the n-best solution from the P-graph optimized solutions. This gives a once-off understanding of the conditions necessary to have high target response (diabetes level) considering machine learning models with cross-validation.

Figure 3: (a) PLS supervised modelling of the diabetes dataset and the task of maximizing diabetes response to find important factors. (b) Network representation of PLS. (c) Solution identified by Pgraph library.

3.3 Process Optimization with Embedded Machine Learning Models

In this section, a case study of gas reservoir selection problem is presented to demonstrate the direct application of P-graph with embedded machine learning models. Firstly, 3 different gas reservoirs with different constituent and water content are available to be extracted in an upstream oil and gas facility. It is necessary to consider the combination of reservoir for extraction without causing hydrate formation in the pipelines and equipment (see Fig 4(a)). Prediction of hydrate formation is a difficult task that requires machine learning model (Zahedi et al., 2009). A decision tree classifier was trained on methane (%), ethane (%), moisture (%), pressure and temperature on stream to predict hydrate formation (Fig 4(b)) with over 80% accuracy (Fig. 4(c)). The machine learning-hybridized P-graph model is represented in Fig. 4(d) which consists of sections which deals with resource allocation, decision tree, and decisions relating to formation of hydrate. By solving the problem, reservoir 2 (orange) was selected to give the highest economic value of 9960 Euro/h while giving no hydrates in the pipeline.

Figure 4: (a) Reservoir resource allocation problem with hydrate detection consideration (b) trained decision tree classifier. (c) Corresponding receiver operating characteristic (ROC) curves. (d) Maximal structure of machine learning-hybridized P-graph network. (e) Solution #1 of problem demonstrating resource selected and decision pathway.

4 Conclusion

This *short communication* introduces a new *Pgraph Python* library which acts as an interface for the classical P-graph framework. The advantage of linking P-graph framework to the Python modern programming ecosystem is (i) the seamless automation enabled for topological optimization problems, and (ii) new possibilities of data-driven algorithms to be embedded into the P-graph framework without scalability issues. These two advantages have been demonstrated via examples with open-sourced code in this *short communication*. This opens the potential for an efficient data-driven and topologically optimized future for chemistry and chemical engineering.

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References

- Ali, R.A., Nor, N., Nik, L., Azlina, W., Abdul, W., Sani, N.S., Lam, H.L., 2022. A Hybrid P-Graph And WEKA Approach In Decision-Making : Waste Conversion Technologies Selection 26, 261–267. [https://doi.org/10.6180/jase.202302_26\(2\).0012](https://doi.org/10.6180/jase.202302_26(2).0012)
- Efron, B., Hastie, T., Johnstone, I., Tibshirani, R., 2004. Least angle regression. *Ann. Stat.* 32. <https://doi.org/10.1214/009053604000000067>
- Fan, L.T., Lin, Y.-C., Shafie, S., Bertok, B., Friedler, F., 2012. Exhaustive Identification of Feasible Pathways of the Reaction Catalyzed by a Catalyst with Multiactive Sites via a Highly Effective Graph-Theoretic Algorithm: Application to Ethylene Hydrogenation. *Ind. Eng. Chem. Res.* 51, 2548–2552. <https://doi.org/10.1021/ie200718w>
- Feng, G., Fan, L.T., Seib, P.A., Bertok, B., Kalotai, L., Friedler, F., 2003. Graph-Theoretic Method for the Algorithmic Synthesis of Azeotropic-Distillation Systems. *Ind. Eng. Chem. Res.* 42, 3602–3611. <https://doi.org/10.1021/ie0207818>
- Friedler, F., Orosz, Á., Pimentel Losada, J., 2022. P-graphs for Process Systems Engineering, 1st ed, P-graphs for Process Systems Engineering. Springer International Publishing, Cham. <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-92216-0>
- Friedler, F., Tarjan, K., Huang, Y.W., Fan, L.T., 1993. Graph-theoretic approach to process synthesis: Polynomial algorithm for maximal structure generation. *Comput. Chem. Eng.* 17, 929–942.

[https://doi.org/10.1016/0098-1354\(93\)80074-W](https://doi.org/10.1016/0098-1354(93)80074-W)

Friedler, F., Tarján, K., Huang, Y.W., Fan, L.T., 1992. Graph-theoretic approach to process synthesis: axioms and theorems. *Chem. Eng. Sci.* 47, 1973–1988. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0009-2509\(92\)80315-4](https://doi.org/10.1016/0009-2509(92)80315-4)

Hagberg, A.A., Schult, D.A., Swart, P.J., 2008. Exploring network structure, dynamics, and function using NetworkX, in: 7th Python in Science Conference (SciPy 2008).

How, B.S., Hong, B.H., Lam, H.L., Friedler, F., 2016. Synthesis of multiple biomass corridor via decomposition approach: A P-graph application. *J. Clean. Prod.*
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2015.12.021>

How, B.S., Teng, S.Y., Leong, W.D., Ng, W.P.Q., Lim, C.H., Ngan, S.L., Lam, H.L., 2019. Non-linear Programming via P-graph Framework. *Chem. Eng. Trans.* 76, 499–504.
<https://doi.org/10.3303/CET1976084>

Lam, H.L., Varbanov, P.S., Klemeš, J.J., 2010. Optimisation of regional energy supply chains utilising renewables: P-graph approach. *Comput. Chem. Eng.* 34, 782–792.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compchemeng.2009.11.020>

Lim, J.Y., How, B.S., Teng, S.Y., Leong, W.D., Tang, J.P., Lam, H.L., Yoo, C.K., 2021. Multi-objective lifecycle optimization for oil palm fertilizer formulation: A hybrid P-graph and TOPSIS approach. *Resour. Conserv. Recycl.* 166, 105357.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.resconrec.2020.105357>

Liu, J., Fan, L.T., Seib, P., Friedler, F., Bertok, B., 2004. Downstream Process Synthesis for Biochemical Production of Butanol, Ethanol, and Acetone from Grains: Generation of Optimal and Near-Optimal Flowsheets with Conventional Operating Units. *Biotechnol. Prog.* 20, 1518–1527. <https://doi.org/10.1021/bp049845v>

Ondruška, V., How, B.S., Netolický, M., Máša, V., Teng, S.Y., 2022. Resource optimisation in aquaponics facility via process monitoring and graph-theoretical approach. *Carbon Resour.*

Convers. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.crcon.2022.04.003>

Peters, M., Timmerhaus, K., West, R., 2016. Equipment costs Plant Design and Economics for chemical Engineers - 5th Edition [WWW Document]. McGraw Hill Educ.

Tan, J.X., Tan, H.S., Peter Affery, A., Ong, I.Y.B., Foo, D.C.Y., Aviso, K.B., Tan, R.R., Yoo, C., 2021. A P-Graph approach for the synthesis of hydrogen networks with pressure and impurity constraints. *Int. J. Hydrogen Energy* 46, 29198–29215.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijhydene.2020.08.286>

Wold, H., 1980. Model Construction and Evaluation When Theoretical Knowledge Is Scarce. Theory and Application of Partial Least Squares, in: Jan Kmenta and James B. Ramsey, E. (Ed.), Evaluation of Econometric Models. Academic Press, pp. 47–74.

Zahedi, G., Karami, Z., Yaghoobi, H., 2009. Prediction of hydrate formation temperature by both statistical models and artificial neural network approaches. *Energy Convers. Manag.*

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enconman.2009.04.005>

In []:

```
!pip install git+https://github.com/tsyet12/Pgraph --quiet
```

In []:

```
#import all libraries
from Pgraph.Pgraph import Pgraph #This is our Pgraph library
import networkx as nx
import matplotlib.pyplot as plt
```

In []:

```
##### STEP 1 : Problem Specification #####
G = nx.DiGraph()
G.add_node("M1",names="Product D",type='product',flow_rate_lower_bound=100, flow_rate_upper_bound=100)
G.add_node("M2",names="Chemical A",type='raw_material',price=200,flow_rate_lower_bound=0)
G.add_node("M3",names="Chemical B", type='raw_material',price=100,flow_rate_lower_bound=0)
G.add_node("M4",names="Chemical C", type='raw_material',price=10,flow_rate_lower_bound=0)
G.add_node("O1",names="Reactor 1",fix_cost=2000, proportional_cost=400)
G.add_node("O2", names="Reactor 2",fix_cost=1000, proportional_cost=400)
G.add_edge("M2","O1", weight = 1)
G.add_edge("M3","O2", weight = 1)
G.add_edge("M4","O2", weight = 2)
G.add_edge("O1","M1", weight = 0.7)
G.add_edge("O2","M1", weight = 0.9)
ME=[["O1","O2"]] #Reactor 1 and Reactor 2 are mutually excluded. Only one can be chosen as solution.
#####
```

In []:

```
#### Step 2: Setup Solver ####
P=Pgraph(problem_network=G, mutual_exclusion=ME, solver="INSIDEOUT",max_sol=100)
#####
```

In []:

```
#### Step 2.1: Plot Problem #####
ax1=P.plot_problem(figsize=(5,5))
ax1.set_xlim(0,200)
plt.show()
#####
```


In []:

```
#### Step 3: Run ####
P.run()
#####
```

Installing wine dependencies (only for Linux), this may take longer for the first time. Use skip_wine=True if you are sure wine is installed.

In []:

```
#### Step 3.1: Plot Solution#####
total_sol_num=P.get_sol_num()
for i in range(total_sol_num): # Here we loop through all the solutions to plot everything
    ax=P.plot_solution(sol_num=i) #Plot Solution Function
    ax.set_xlim(0,200)
    plt.show()
#####
```


In []:

```
#### Step 3.2: Export to P-graph Studio ####
```

```
from google.colab import files #This is only for google colab
string = P.to_studio(path='./',verbose=False) #export to p-graph studio
files.download("./studio_file.pgsx") #download for google colab
#####
```

#Note: Please be reminded to press "Generate Layout" button in P-graph Studio after opening

In [2]:

```
!pip install git+https://github.com/tsyet12/Pgraph --quiet
```

Building wheel for Pgraph (setup.py) ... done

In [3]:

```
!pip install Chemsy --quiet
```

In [4]:

```
#import all libraries
from Pgraph.Pgraph import Pgraph #This is our Pgraph library
import networkx as nx
import matplotlib.pyplot as plt
from sklearn.datasets import load_diabetes
from chemsy.predict import *
from sklearn.preprocessing import MinMaxScaler
```

In [5]:

```
#Make a basic Partial Least Squares Supervised Learning Model
```

```
diabetes = load_diabetes() #load data
```

```
X, y = diabetes.data, diabetes.target
```

```
xscaler=MinMaxScaler() # scale data between 0 to 1
```

```
yscaler=MinMaxScaler()
```

```
X=xscaler.fit_transform(X) #scale
```

```
y=yscaler.fit_transform(y.reshape(-1, 1))
```

```
model=PartialLeastSquaresCV() #partial least squares with cross validation
```

```
model.fit(X,y) #fit model
```

```
B=model.model.coef_ #Get B vector of PLSCV
```

In [6]:

```
##### STEP 1 : Problem Specification #####
```

```
G = nx.DiGraph()
```

```
G.add_node("M1",names="combine",type='intermediate',flow_rate_lower_bound=0, flow_rate_upper_bound=0,price=0)
```

```
global_count=2
```

```
for i in range(B.shape[0]):
```

```
    if B[i][0]>=0:
```

```
        G.add_node("M"+str(global_count),names=diabetes.feature_names[i],type='raw_material',flow_rate_lower_bound=0, flow_rate_upper_bound=1,price=0)
```

```
        G.add_node("O"+str(global_count),names=diabetes.feature_names[i])
```

```
        G.add_edge("M"+str(global_count),"O"+str(global_count), weight = 1, price=0)
```

```
        G.add_edge("O"+str(global_count),"M1", weight = B[i][0])
```

```
        global_count=global_count+1
```

```
    else:
```

```
        G.add_node("M"+str(global_count),names=diabetes.feature_names[i],type='product',flow_rate_lower_bound=0, flow_rate_upper_bound=1,price=0)
```

```
        G.add_node("O"+str(global_count),names=diabetes.feature_names[i])
```

```
        G.add_edge("O"+str(global_count),"M"+str(global_count), weight = 1, price=0)
```

```
        G.add_edge("M1","O"+str(global_count), weight = -B[i][0])
```

```
        global_count=global_count+1
```

```
G.add_node("O"+str(global_count),names="sum")
```

```
G.add_edge("M1","O"+str(global_count), weight = 1)
```

```
G.add_edge("O"+str(global_count),"M"+str(global_count+1), weight = 1)
```

```
global_count=global_count+1
```

```
G.add_node("M"+str(global_count),names="Prediction",type='product',price=100,flow_rate_lower_bound=0, flow_rate_upper_bound=10000)
```

In [7]:

```
#### Step 2: Setup Solver ####
P=Pgraph(problem_network=G, mutual_exclusion=[[ ]], solver="INSIDEOUT",max_sol=100)
#####
```

In [8]:

```
#### Step 2.1: Plot Problem #####
ax1=P.plot_problem(figsize=(15,10), titlepos=1)
plt.show()
#####
```


In [9]:

```
#### Step 3: Run ####
P.run()
#####
```

Installing wine dependencies (only for Linux), this may take longer for the first time. Use skip_wine=True if you are sure wine is installed.

In [12]:

```
#### Step 3.1: Plot Solution#####
for i in range(3): # Here we plot the 3 top solution
    ax=P.plot_solution(sol_num=i,figsize=(15,10), titlepos=1) #Plot Solution Function
    plt.show()
#####
```


Solution #2 Total Costs=-122.064

Solution #3 Total Costs=-116.072

In [11]:

```
#### Step 3.2: Export to P-graph Studio ####
from google.colab import files #This is only for google colab
string = P.to_studio(path='./',verbose=False) #export to p-graph studio
files.download("./studio_file.pgxs") #download for google colab
#####
```

#Note: Please be reminded to press "Generate Layout" button in P-graph Studio after opening

Pgraph (/github/tsyet12/Pgraph/tree/main)
/ P_graph_Example_3.ipynb (/github/tsyet12/Pgraph/tree/main/P_graph_Example_3.ipynb)

 Open in Colab

(https://colab.research.google.com/github/tsyet12/Pgraph/blob/main/P_graph_Example_3.ipynb).

In [1]:

```
!pip install git+https://github.com/tsyet12/Pgraph --quiet
```

```
Building wheel for ProcessGraph (setup.py) ... done
```

In [19]:

```
#import all libraries  
from Pgraph.Pgraph import Pgraph #This is our Pgraph Library  
import networkx as nx  
import matplotlib.pyplot as plt  
import os  
import pandas as pd  
import numpy as np  
from sklearn.model_selection import train_test_split  
from sklearn.tree import DecisionTreeClassifier  
from sklearn import tree  
import matplotlib.pyplot as plt  
from sklearn.ensemble import ExtraTreesClassifier  
from sklearn import metrics  
from sklearn.metrics import confusion_matrix  
from sklearn.tree._tree import TREE_LEAF, TREE_UNDEFINED
```

In [13]:

```
## Get the data #####  
  
data=pd.read_csv('Hydrates2.csv')  
data=data.drop([0,1])  
data.iloc[:,6]=data.iloc[:,6].where(data.iloc[:,6]!=2)  
data=data.dropna()  
data=data.iloc[:-1,:]  
X=data.iloc[:,1:6]  
y=data.iloc[:,6]  
feature_names=list(data.columns)[1:6]
```

In [14]:

```

#Some useful functions for pruning

def is_leaf(inner_tree, index):
    # Check whether node is leaf node
    return (inner_tree.children_left[index] == TREE_LEAF and
            inner_tree.children_right[index] == TREE_LEAF)

def prune_index(inner_tree, decisions, index=0):
    # Start pruning from the bottom - if we start from the top, we might miss
    # nodes that become leaves during pruning.
    # Do not use this directly - use prune_duplicate_leaves instead.
    if not is_leaf(inner_tree, inner_tree.children_left[index]):
        prune_index(inner_tree, decisions, inner_tree.children_left[index])
    if not is_leaf(inner_tree, inner_tree.children_right[index]):
        prune_index(inner_tree, decisions, inner_tree.children_right[index])

    # Prune children if both children are leaves now and make the same decision:
    if (is_leaf(inner_tree, inner_tree.children_left[index]) and
        is_leaf(inner_tree, inner_tree.children_right[index]) and
        (decisions[index] == decisions[inner_tree.children_left[index]]) and
        (decisions[index] == decisions[inner_tree.children_right[index]])):
        # turn node into a leaf by "unlinking" its children
        inner_tree.children_left[index] = TREE_LEAF
        inner_tree.children_right[index] = TREE_LEAF
        inner_tree.feature[index] = TREE_UNDEFINED

def prune_duplicate_leaves mdl):
    # Remove leaves if both
    decisions = mdl.tree_.value.argmax(axis=2).flatten().tolist() # Decision for each
    prune_index(mdl.tree_, decisions)
    return mdl

```

In [16]:

```

##### TRAIN DECISION TREE AND LOOK AT ACCURACY METRICS #####
X_train, X_test, y_train, y_test = train_test_split(X, y, test_size=0.25, random_state=
clf = DecisionTreeClassifier(criterion='entropy', max_leaf_nodes=None, max_depth=7, ran
clf.fit(X_train, y_train)
clf=prune_duplicate_leaves(clf)
y_pred=clf.predict(X_test)

print("Accuracy (Train):", metrics.accuracy_score(y_train, clf.predict(X_train)))
print("Accuracy (Test):", metrics.accuracy_score(y_test, y_pred))

```

Accuracy (Train): 0.8014809751651857

Accuracy (Test): 0.8019822282980178

In [20]:

```
##### STEP 1 : Problem Specification #####

n_nodes = clf.tree_.node_count
children_left = clf.tree_.children_left
children_right = clf.tree_.children_right
feature = clf.tree_.feature
threshold = clf.tree_.threshold
value=clf.classes_[[np.argmax(x) for x in clf.tree_.value]]
classes=clf.classes_

node_depth = np.zeros(shape=n_nodes, dtype=np.int64)
is_leaves = np.zeros(shape=n_nodes, dtype=bool)
stack = [(0, 0)] # start with the root node id (0) and its depth (0)

while len(stack) > 0:
    # `pop` ensures each node is only visited once
    node_id, depth = stack.pop()
    #print(node_id,depth)
    node_depth[node_id] = depth

    is_split_node = children_left[node_id] != children_right[node_id]
    # If a split node, append left and right children and depth to `stack`
    # so we can loop through them
    if is_split_node:
        stack.append((children_left[node_id], depth + 1))
        stack.append((children_right[node_id], depth + 1))

    else:
        is_leaves[node_id] = True

G = nx.DiGraph()

ME=[]
## Unique Features as Input Material Nodes
unique_features=list(set(feature))
unique_features=[x for x in unique_features if x>=0]
global_count=n_nodes+1

for x in unique_features:
    G.add_node("M"+str(global_count),names=feature_names[x],type='intermediate',flow_r
    G.add_node("O"+str(global_count),names=feature_names[x])
    G.add_edge("M"+str(global_count),"O"+str(global_count), weight = 1, prices=0)
    global_count=global_count+1

leaf=[-2]*len(classes)

for i in range(n_nodes):
    if is_leaves[i] or feature[i]==-2: #leave or pruned
        if i in children_left or i in children_right:
            decision=int(value[i])
            if leaf[decision]>=0:
                G.add_edge("O"+str(i),"M"+str(leaf[decision]), weight = 1, prices=0)
            else:
                G.add_edge("O"+str(i),"M"+str(i), weight = 1, prices=0)
                G.add_node("M"+str(i),names=str(decision),type='intermediate',flow_rat
                leaf[decision]=i
        else:
            node=i
```

```

features=feature[i]
feature_idx=unique_features.index(features)
left=children_left[i]
right=children_right[i]
thresholds=threshold[i]
suc_type=None
suc_list=list(G.successors("0"+str(feature_idx+n_nodes+1)))
if suc_list != []:
    try:
        suc_type=G.nodes()[suc_list[0]]['type']
    except:
        pass #suc_type=None
if suc_type!='intermediate':
    G.add_edge("0"+str(feature_idx+n_nodes+1),"M"+str(node), weight = 1, price
    G.add_node("M"+str(node),names="M"+str(node),type='intermediate',flow_rate
    G.add_edge("M"+str(node),"0"+str(node), weight = 1, prices=0)
else:
    G.add_edge(suc_list[0],"0"+str(node), weight = 1, prices=0)

G.add_node("0"+str(node),names="0"+str(node))

G.add_edge("0"+str(node),"M"+str(global_count), weight = 1, prices=0)
G.add_node("M"+str(global_count),names="M"+str(global_count),type='intermediat

#left
G.add_edge("M"+str(global_count),"0"+str(global_count+1), weight = 1, prices=0
G.add_node("0"+str(global_count+1),names="0"+str(global_count+1),capacity_lowe
G.add_edge("0"+str(global_count+1),"M"+str(global_count+1), weight = 1, prices
G.add_node("M"+str(global_count+1),names="M"+str(global_count+1),type='interme
G.add_edge("M"+str(global_count+1),"0"+str(left), weight = 0.001, prices=0)
G.add_node("0"+str(left),names="0"+str(left),capacity_lower_bound=0, capacity_

#right
G.add_edge("M"+str(global_count),"0"+str(global_count+2), weight = 1, prices=0
G.add_node("0"+str(global_count+2),names="0"+str(global_count+2),capacity_lowe
G.add_edge("0"+str(global_count+2),"M"+str(global_count+2), weight = 1, prices
G.add_node("M"+str(global_count+2),names="M"+str(global_count+2),type='interme
G.add_edge("M"+str(global_count+2),"0"+str(right), weight = 0.001, prices=0)
G.add_node("0"+str(right),names="0"+str(right),capacity_lower_bound=0, capacit

ME.append(["0"+str(global_count+1),"0"+str(global_count+2)])
global_count=global_count+3
#####

```


In [29]:

```

####Plot the decision Tree (Up to depth of 4)###
plt.figure(figsize=(22,6))
tree.plot_tree(clf,max_depth=4,fontsize=10)
plt.tight_layout()
plt.show()

```


In [36]:

```

#### SETUP P-graph problem and export to P-graph ####
P=Pgraph(problem_network=G, mutual_exclusion=ME, solver="INSIDEOUT",max_sol=100)
P.to_studio(path='./',file_name='pg.pgsx',verbose=False)

```

Out[36]:

```

'<?xml version="1.0" encoding="utf-16"?>\n<PGraph xmlns:xsi="http://www.

```

In [38]:

```

from google.colab import files
files.download('pg.pgsx') #Download to add resource optimization manually
#Note: Manual operation is just for demonstration, you can also automate it if you wan

```